

RAW DATA SET

Raw Table S1: Biological index values of soil fauna in non-invaded and invaded areas.

Indices	Non-invaded area			Invaded area		
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3
Species	22	22	19	16	18	14
Density	178	202	143	68	87	50
Richness index	4.05	3.39	3.63	3.55	3.80	3.32
Shannon-Weiner index	0.95	0.98	0.98	0.86	0.85	0.78
Evenness index	3.09	2.94	2.94	2.38	2.46	2.07
Similarity index	9.76		6.92		8.29	

This dataset was used to build **Table 2**

Raw Table S2: Comparison of the survival rates (%) of different soil fauna species by *A. gracilipes*.

soil fauna	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	before	after	before	after	before	after
Termite workers	124	0	114	0	131	0
Isopod	5	3	5	3	5	4
Crickets	5	0	5	1	5	0
Cockroaches	5	0	5	0	5	0
Snails	5	5	5	5	5	5
Millipedes	5	5	5	5	5	5
Earthworms	5	0	5	0	5	0

This dataset was used to build **Fig. 1**.

Raw Table S3: Mean predation time (minutes) required by *A. gracilipes* to prey on different soil fauna species.

Soil fauna	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3
Termite workers	0.48	0.54	1
Isopod	3	3	3
Crickets	15	14	15
Cockroaches	16	16	14
Snails	0	0	0
Millipedes	0	0	0
Earthworms	30	37	35

This dataset was used to build **Fig. 2**.

Raw Table S4: Comparison of the survival rates (%) of different native ant species by *A. gracilipes*.

Native ant	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	before	after	before	before	after	before
<i>Carebara diversa</i>	147	126	142	134	152	125
<i>Camponotus festinus</i>	20	5	24	3	25	6
<i>Stigmatomma reclinatum</i>	22	8	22	7	23	8

This dataset was used to build **Fig. 3**.

Raw Table S5: Mean predation time (minutes) required by *A. gracilipes* to capture different native ant species.

Native ant	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3
<i>Carebara diversa</i>	3	4	4
<i>Camponotus festinus</i>	4.36	4	5
<i>Stigmatomma reclinatum</i>	5.36	6.21	5.84

This dataset was used to build **Fig. 4**.

Raw Table S6: Comparison of soil fauna abundance between uninvaded and invaded areas.

soil fauna	Replicate 1		Replicate 2		Replicate 3	
	non- invaded area	invaded areas	non- invaded area	invaded areas	non- invaded area	invaded areas
Termite workers	37	0	100	20	0	0
Isopod	17	11	30	7	24	10
Crickets	0	0	4	0	5	1
Cockroaches	5	6	9	6	1	1
Snails	20	18	17	16	16	17
Millipedes	7	4	11	9	1	2
Earthworms	7	0	6	0	3	0

This dataset was used to build **Fig. 5**.